

Supplementary Information 7 – IRMS methodology

Aragonite samples drilled from the outside of the shells of **C2**, **E2** and **E3** and on cross sections through the columnella of **C2** and **E1** were analyzed for stable carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) isotope compositions. Care was taken to exclude any aragonite that was geochemically altered during the fossilization process (see **SI_preservation**). Aliquots of 100 μg of powdered aragonite were prepared in glass vials and introduced into the NuCarb carbonate preparation device (Nu Instruments Ltd, Wrexham, UK). Here samples were reacted under vacuum with an excess of phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) to produce CO_2 gas, which was subsequently cryogenically purified in a series of water traps and cold fingers before being introduced into the NuPerspective Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer (IRMS; Nu Instruments Ltd, Wrexham, UK) via a dual inlet system.

Ratios of stable carbon and oxygen isotopes were measured relative to an in-house CO_2 reference gas. Stable isotope data was corrected for variations in sample volume, linearity of the mass spectrometer and reproducibility using repeated measurements of the IA603 certified reference material (International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria), which were treated as samples throughout the measurement procedure. These corrections allowed stable isotope values to be reported in delta notation relative to the Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite reference values ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in ‰VPDB) according to the formula:

$$\delta^n X = \left(\frac{\frac{nX_{\text{sample}}}{mX_{\text{sample}}}}{\frac{nX_{\text{VPDB}}}{mX_{\text{VPDB}}}} - 1 \right) * 1000\text{‰}$$

Here, n is the mass of the rare isotope (^{13}C or ^{18}O) and X is the element (C or O).

In order to test the accuracy of IRMS measurements, three other certified reference materials were analyzed in the same procedure: NBS-19 ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$: 1.95‰VPDB; $\delta^{18}\text{O}$: -2.20‰VPDB; International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria; Friedman et al., 1982); MAR2 ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$: 3.41‰VPDB; $\delta^{18}\text{O}$: 0.13‰VPDB; in-house relative to NBS-19) and NBS-18 ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$: -5.014‰VPDB; $\delta^{18}\text{O}$: -23.2‰VPDB; International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria; Friedman et al., 1982), bracketing the measurements in this study. Measured stable isotope ratios very closely approximate the certified values of the standards (slope of 0.992 for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and 0.999 for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ with R^2 values of 1.000 and 0.999 respectively; see **Fig. S1**). This demonstrates that IRMS measurements were very accurate. Reproducibility of these measurements on the IA603 standard were better than 0.1‰ for both stable isotope ratios.

Figure S1: Results of measurements on IA603, MAR2, NBS-18 and NBS19 demonstrating high accuracy and reproducibility of stable isotope measurements in this study

In order to test the growth model of *Campanile* gastropod shells constructed based on microscopic observations and based on the model proposed by Tojo and Ohno (1999), isotope ratios of samples

taken from the outside of the shell of **C2** as well as from the columnella were compared (see **Fig. S2**). This comparison shows that, while $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of simultaneously precipitated aragonite samples are reproducible when measured in different parts of the shell, there is a notable offset between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of samples from the outside of the shell and the columnella. The latter demonstrates a potential offset caused by vital effects. The fact that the offset in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is negative near the bottom of the shell and positive near the apex seems to indicate that these might be a sampling bias when sampling either the outside of the shell or the columnella due to aragonite from the ingrowths in the whorls might get mixed into the samples more readily near the apex due to the thinning of the shell walls. The same issues of sample mixing increase the scatter of IRMS data of columnella samples compared to samples taken on the outside of the shell, because columnella sampling is more likely to mix aragonite precipitated at different times due to the complexity of shell growth in the columnella (see **SI_shellgrowth**).

Figure S2: Overview of IRMS measurements on the outside of the shell (black) and in the columnella (red) of **C2**. A green line shows the approximated oxygen isotope curve created using the model of Judd et al. (2018).

References

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- Tojo, B., Ohno, T., 1999. Continuous growth-line sequences in gastropod shells. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 145, 183–191.